

End-to-End SDN/NFV Orchestration of Video Analytics Using Edge and Cloud Computing over Programmable Optical Networks

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Abstract: This paper proposes the introduction of SDN-enabled containers to support the deployment of SDN/NFV applications located at the network edge, which are able to trigger on-demand connectivity services. A video analytics use case is demonstrated.

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1. Introduction

End-to-end network latency has a very negative impact when the cloud resources (typically running in large-scale Data Centers – DC) are used to run delay-sensitive virtual applications such as real-time video analysis, video-on-demand or virtual desktop. Moreover, the transport of high data rates related to bandwidth requiring applications towards the DC also increases network utilization. Moreover, in order to reduce the end-user latencies, and optimize and rationalize the usage of network resources, distributed lightweight computing resources are needed in different network locations, closer to the network edge [1]. It is in this sense that edge computing (also known as fog computing) is necessary in order to reduce the impact of the network latency and reduce bandwidth usage, as data is processed where it is generated, reducing the necessity of bulk data transmissions.

As the compute resources at the edge are commonly limited, typically running in lightweight industrialized servers (e.g., to fit in street cabinets), we propose to use SDN-enabled Linux containers as the preferred compute virtualization solution, thus reducing performance overhead below 5% [2]. Docker is a de-facto standard for container management. Its integration of container networking with SDN has been previously demonstrated [2]. Docker containers are able to run generalized lightweight applications, thus allowing to dynamically run on-demand virtual applications. Extensions to SDN/NFV Orchestrator are needed to run any kind of applications, and it also requires a novel degree of dynamicity towards the underlying network resources through network programmability.

In order to demonstrate the advantages of the proposed solution, we propose the use case of video analytics on a Close Circuit TV (CCTV) running at the edge of the network (see Fig.1.a). Standard video analytics require a constant bitrate of 240 Kbps towards a DC running the necessary video surveillance applications [3]. The overall usage of CCTV cameras easily justifies the need for Gbps for transmission of raw data. We propose to move the video analytics applications to the network edge nodes. This allows us to process the video stream closer to the CCTV sources, and only request transmission of data towards the DC in case an event is detected by the application. This approach might save 90% of the bandwidth usage of the network, as events will discretely trigger connectivity services. A video storage application is run in the core data center. When the video analytics app detects a movement, it sends the video in real-time to the core DC in order to be stored and processed.

Transport API (T-API) has recently been proposed as the northbound interface for a transport SDN controller. It is able to provide End-to-End (E2E) transport service provisioning and orchestration across multiple domains with heterogeneous transport and control plane technologies [4]. T-API can be used to trigger the on-demand request for connectivity service between the proposed video analytics application and the DC resources.

We have previously presented a joint SDN/NFV orchestration mechanism of Cloud and Network resources [5]. In this paper, we propose: a) to include SDN-enabled containers in order to better orchestrate the underlying infrastructure (including computation resources) for future edge virtual services, b) to deploy a SDN/NFV Orchestrator to dynamically deploy virtual applications on top of containers at network edge, or virtual machines in the core DC, and provide the required connectivity among the virtual applications in order to offer end-to-end services. The usage of these cloud resources at the edge will free network resources.

2. SDN-enabled containers for network edge and their integration in a transport SDN/NFV architecture

As explained, the introduction of SDN-enabled containers allows an efficient usage of compute resources. Fig.1.b shows the proposed architecture of an SDN-enabled container. On top of an industrialized server hardware, a container-enabled host operative system is executed. In order to offer the necessary internal and external

Fig.1. a) Use case for edge video analytics, b) SDN-enabled containers architecture for edge node, c) Extended SDN/NFV architecture

connectivity (e.g., inside the edge node and towards the edge network) to the virtualized compute resources, a software switch (such as OpenVSwitch) is used. Docker Library and daemon allows us to dynamically offer isolated guest containers and interconnect the containers towards the software switch. An edge node SDN controller is responsible for handling the network connectivity and establishing the necessary flows in the software switch. Finally, we have introduced a container agent (docker-agent) in order to provide a YANG-based REST API, which offers the necessary container and network services to both the cloud/edge and network orchestrators [6].

Fig 1.c shows the proposed E2E architecture. An extended SDN/NFV Orchestrator (SDN/NFV-O) is able to deploy virtualized functions (VF) on top of a hybrid infrastructure consisting of compute, storage and network resources. It might also receive connectivity service requests from applications (such as VFs) using T-API. VFs are deployed using dedicated VF Manager, who is responsible for the VF lifecycle. In this paper, two VF have been developed: a) a video analytics application [7], which is responsible for processing the camera image feed by detecting movement (using Gaussian blur filters, differential image and contour detection), requesting connectivity towards the DC and storing the suspicious videos, and b) the video storage application running in a remote DC. An Integrated Cloud/Edge and Network Orchestrator are responsible for offering the necessary integration offering the services for a virtualized infrastructure manager in a MANO architecture [5]. The Cloud/Edge orchestrator is responsible for abstracting the compute resources, depending on their network domain interconnection (DC or Edge node resources) and their compute resource virtualization mechanism (container-based or hypervisor), and to provide a common API to deploy on top of the abstracted compute resources the necessary VFs. The multi-domain network orchestrator is an SDN controller which is responsible for the underlying technologies dedicated controllers used in each heterogeneous network domain. A new plugin has been introduced in order to handle the internal and external connectivity in the edge node, through the edge node SDN controller. Different network segments are considered in the proposed architecture, including a metro network with edge packet aggregation nodes with compute resources, optical core networks and a DC network. From the computing perspective an edge node and a core DC have been considered. Finally, a CCTV directly connected to the edge node is introduced in order to provide the necessary video feed.

In the following subsections, we describe the proposed message exchange workflow, focusing on:

a) Provisioning resources at the edge node and DC (Fig.2.a, Steps 1-3). A client requests the video analytics and video storage services to the SDN/NFV-O, which triggers each responsible VF manager. First, the video storage VF is deployed in a virtual machine (VM) located in the DC (step 1), as its assigned IP address must be specified as configuration parameter to the video analytics application. In step 2, a container is deployed in the edge node. Finally, the video analytics application is run, and video feed is directly received from the CCTV camera (step 3). Then, the video analytics application is able to detect movement and to trigger the necessary connectivity services, if needed.

b) In-operation application-triggered connectivity services towards core DC (Fig.2.a, Steps 4-6). Once a motion event is detected, the application triggers the necessary T-API connectivity services (step 4) towards the SDN/NFV-O, which redirects the connectivity service request towards the multi-domain network orchestrator, which triggers the necessary LSPs and the necessary flows in the underlying network domains. The video analysis application selects and processes the video frames which are suspicious and uploads them into the video storage application running on the DC (step 5). Finally, the connectivity service is removed, freeing the network resources.

Fig.2. a) Message exchange workflow for edge video analytics, b) Wireshark captures

3. Experimental demonstration of End-to-End SDN/NFV Orchestration of Video Analytics

The proposed SDN/NFV edge node has been developed using an Intel NUC 6i7KYK2 (including an i7 processor), with 32Gb RAM and 512 Gb SSD. Several USB to Ethernet port converters have been included in order to extend the node switching capabilities. The edge node follows the presented architecture described in Fig.1.b, including Docker, OpenVSwitch, Ryu SDN controller and a docker agent [6].

The edge node has been connected to the Cloud Computing platform of the ADRENALINE Testbed (Fig.1.a) [5], where OpenStack Havana release has been deployed into servers with 2 x Intel Xeon E5-2420 and 32GB RAM each. Four OpenFlow switches have also been deployed. Each Data Center border switch has a 10 Gb/s XFP tunable transponder and OFS. Finally, the GMPLS-controlled optical network is composed of an all-optical WSON with 2 ROADMs and 2 OXC's providing reconfigurable end-to-end lightpaths.

The implementations of the SDN/NFV-O, VF [7], VF managers, Cloud/Edge and Network Orchestrator, and multi-domain network orchestrator use Python. Several internal REST interfaces are offered between the different components. In this paper we have used the Transport API to interact between VF and the SDN/NFV-O. The Transport API information model is described in YANG, and it uses RESTconf as transport protocol. RESTconf allows using the Transport API as an HTTP REST API.

Fig.2.b shows the wireshark captures of the exchanged messages at both the SDN/NFV-O and VF. Firstly, the SDN/NFV-O requests the necessary VF resources, and the VF managers trigger their execution. Once the video analytics is running and a suspicious movement is detected, the VF requests a bidirectional E2E service call request. The multi-domain network orchestrator is responsible for computing an E2E path. Its virtual network topology manager decomposes the computed E2E path in order to request a call service to the underlying network domains. Once established, the processed video is transmitted using SCP (with SSL encryption). Finally, the connectivity service is removed.

The required time to create a VM is around 8.5s. A container is created within 400ms. Finally, the connectivity service through the underlying networks domains requires 730ms, due to the fact that optical connections were previously established.

4. Conclusions

We have proposed an SDN-enabled container-based edge node and its integration in Cloud/Edge and network resources. We have presented a use case for reducing network bandwidth utilization up to 90% by deploying video analytics at the network edge using an extended SDN/NFV architecture.

5. Acknowledgments

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6. References

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